

KT4D

Knowledge Technologies
for Democracy

KT4D Social Risk Toolkit Module B: AI, trust and awareness – AI and the valuation of human productions

D3.1 MOD. B

December 2025

Funded by
the European Union

This document is part of the deliverable *KT4D Social Risk Toolkit - Modules A, B, and C (Version 1)* (2024) authored by Morisseau, T., & Lima, E., and accessible <https://zenodo.org/records/11491486>

Deliverable Abstract

The integration of artificial intelligence in multiple aspects of our daily lives poses a great challenge in shaping civic participation within societies. Effective civic engagement finds its foundation in the empowerment of citizens who actively participate in public discourse, and in the articulation of their viewpoints. Understanding the dynamics that underpin trust in democratic institutions in this new context is thus important.

Module B focuses on the risks AI poses for social fairness and trust: how the use of AI-based tools can generate inequality or dishonesty, particularly when human productions differ in nature (e.g. creative vs. repetitive tasks), and how such dynamics impact trust between individuals and institutions.

Through a comprehensive exploration and assessment, modules A, B and C of KT4D's Social Risk Toolkit will seek to address an important challenge: identify exactly where regulation is needed to ensure that AI benefits society as a whole, and identify the conditions for trust in social institutions, in order to guarantee effective public debate and societal choices are made by citizens themselves.

The information in this document reflects only the author's views and the European Community is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The information in this document is provided "as is" without guarantee or warranty of any kind, express or implied, including but not limited to the fitness of the information for a particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at his/ her sole risk and liability. This deliverable is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

AI, trust and awareness – AI and the valuation of human productions

The increasing integration of AI in creative, educational, and professional contexts raises fundamental questions about how human effort, skill, and intention are evaluated. Unlike previous tools, AI systems – particularly large language models and generative AI – can produce outputs that closely resemble or even surpass human work in speed, fluency, and sometimes apparent creativity. This challenges traditional notions of authorship, merit, and fairness, and invites a reconsideration of what is genuinely valued in human contributions. Do we value the final product, the intellectual and emotional effort invested in its creation, or the intention behind it? How does the awareness that an artefact was produced by an AI versus a human affect our judgements of quality, authenticity, and moral worth?

This section explores these questions by examining three interrelated dimensions. First, we consider the role of fairness and equity in social evaluations of AI-assisted work, particularly in contexts like education and collaborative environments. Second, we examine what aspects of human work – effort, intentionality, skill – are actually valued, drawing on research from both the arts and broader domains of production. Finally, we reflect on how AI reshapes our relationships with the world and with others, highlighting the limitations of machine-generated outputs in social and epistemic interactions. Together, these analyses shed light on the ways AI influences our perception of human labour, creativity, and collaboration.

1. AI and social fairness

In the course of their evolution, humans have organised themselves in cooperative settings, and it was crucial to share cooperation benefits in a mutually advantageous manner (Baumard, 2011). Those who were too individualistic risked losing partners, while those taking less than their share risked exploitation by partners receiving more than they contributed. This competition resulted in the evolution of a sense of fairness, a cognitive adaptation aiming to equally share cooperation benefits. Evolution favoured fairness because impartial individuals were chosen more often as cooperation partners. Morality may therefore have evolved as an adaptation to an environment marked by competitive dynamics among individuals seeking selection and recruitment in mutually advantageous cooperative interactions (Baumard et al., 2013). **Being fair and reliable made individuals attractive collaborators, leading to the widespread acceptance of fairness in groups.** Thus, people have a natural sense of what is right in distributing benefits, similar to making mutually beneficial agreements. Such behaviour often follows a pattern like social contracts, even in short-term interactions.

The issue of equity, defined as rewarding according to contribution, is a primary concern in the context of AI. In particular, equity is a key component of human fairness, as established in both philosophical discourse and scientific inquiry (Debove et al., 2017). Philosophers have long underscored the importance of the notion that greater effort warrants greater benefits. Psychological research, particularly on distributive justice and equity theory, provides substantial empirical backing for the importance of merit-based rewards (Homans, 1958). A consistent finding is that receiving more or less than one deserves results in distress, prompting efforts to restore equity by adjusting one's contribution (Skitka & Wisneski, 2013). Preferences for income distributions reflecting strong work-

salary correlations, greater rewards for more valuable contributions, and overall meritocratic distributions are evident in both micro- and macro-justice contexts (Baumard et al., 2013). This body of literature serves as a valuable foundation for examining the implications of tools like ChatGPT in diverse social contexts, such as education and work.

The adoption of AI-based tools can be perceived as problematic because it creates more occasions of potential inequality and dishonesty, eroding trust between group members who expect equal treatment for all. In academic contexts, the deployment of AI tools such as ChatGPT raises concerns related to bias and fairness, as well as plagiarism. For instance, according to Reich (2022), AI's ability to generate high-quality essays may erode academic integrity. As AI technologies become easily accessible and increasingly difficult to detect, the potential for students to misuse these tools to cheat on assignments increases.

On the other hand, the use of AI tools like ChatGPT should not necessarily be seen as cheating or plagiarism. They may involve a process of analysis and evaluation by the student, which can be considered as work in its own right. What, then, are the conditions under which these tools can be used with equanimity, so that they are not perceived as potentially leading to a situation that would be perceived as unfair?

To answer this question, research into students' perceptions of what constitutes cheating in the academic context, and the motivations behind it, is quite relevant. For example, in a study by Beasley (2014), students reported that increased awareness of what constitutes cheating and academic dishonesty might have prevented their actions (e.g., through explicit guidelines during exams and assignments; clearer instructions from their professors, etc.). Many students rationalise their cheating by blaming professors, accusing them of failing to emphasise academic integrity or not creating a learning environment that supports honesty. Noteworthy, the use of AI in academic context creates a vacuum that is seen as an opportunity for some, and as an unfair advantage for others.

Broadly changing academic conduct policies to classify AI as a source of plagiarism would be a hasty decision and would be tantamount to throwing the baby out with the bathwater. Both students and teachers should develop an 'AI culture', which includes being aware of AI's pervasiveness, gaining the ability to use it, recognising that everyone can use it, and applying critical thinking to the content produced by AI. Rather than prohibiting AI tools in academia, it could be more beneficial to educate students about AI, its usage, and ethical implications. But whether this means preventing the use of AI tools in certain test conditions, or making use of them by adapting what is asked of students, in the end, it is always a question of reassuring the institution's ability to sanction students fairly.

2. What gives value to human work

As machines increasingly perform tasks that once demanded sustained human effort, questions arise about what should be valued in human work. Effort has long played a central role in how skills are developed and how work is evaluated, not only because of the outcomes it produces, but because of the cognitive, motivational, and intentional processes it reflects. While individuals may willingly delegate tasks they find repetitive or uninteresting, personal effort remains a key driver of learning, expertise, and progress.

This helps explain why technological change rarely leads to the complete abandonment of skills, but rather to their redefinition. Manual arithmetic, for example, has lost much of its practical relevance with the widespread use of calculators. And yet, basic numerical competence remains important, and

greater emphasis is placed on understanding mathematical concepts and knowing how to use computational tools effectively. In such cases, the value of effort shifts from execution to higher-level cognitive control and goal-directed activity.

Writing provides a particularly illustrative example of this transformation. Tools such as large language models can now generate drafts of texts – such as cover letters – within seconds. As a result, the ability to produce such texts from scratch is becoming less distinctive than the ability to evaluate, edit, and refine them. Many writing tasks are thus evolving toward activities that involve judgement, revision, and oversight rather than initial production. As language models continue to improve, this shift is likely to accelerate, leading to a broader reconfiguration of what counts as valuable writing skills.

More generally, the rise of AI has renewed questions about which skills, efforts, and forms of human contribution should be valued. **Research on how people evaluate the value of productions (made by humans or by AI), and art in particular, provides an interesting insight, highlighting what is actually valued.** These studies suggest that evaluations are not based solely on observable features of a product, but also on beliefs about how it was produced and by whom.

For instance, Magni, Park & Chao (2024) showed that people evaluate creativity differently based on whether artefacts are thought to be produced by either AI or humans. They found that there is a context-dependent bias against AI in creative production. Specifically, the bias against AI creative artefacts manifested in some contexts (like paintings) but not others (like advertisement posters and business ideas). A key finding was that AI is perceived to require less effort than humans in the production of creative outputs, and this perception mediates the relationship between the producer's identity and the creativity attributed to the production. Thus, **the perception of effort is an important mediator in the evaluation of creative products.** A folk psychology approach provides a framework for understanding how the identity of the producer affects people's evaluations of creative work: people may perceive artificial agents as lacking emotional and intentional capabilities, which are considered important in creative processes.

Another study (although not about artificial intelligence) highlights the role of effort in evaluating artistic production. Kruger et al. (2004) tested the hypothesis that people used the effort invested in the creation of a product as a heuristic, or mental shortcut, for judging its quality. The idea was that this heuristic is used because direct assessment of quality is often difficult. By manipulating the reported effort put into the creation of various artefacts (like poems, paintings, and suits of armour) and keeping the actual quality constant, the researchers sought to demonstrate that judgements of quality could be swayed erroneously by the perceived effort alone, potentially leading to misjudgement. They made a distinction between self-generated effort, which is associated with dissonance theory, and other-generated effort. The effort heuristic discussed in this paper refers to the judgements about efforts made by others, not by oneself. The authors suggest that the reliance on the effort heuristic is stronger in situations where the quality of the object being evaluated is ambiguous. They argue that in the case of objects like art, where quality is not readily apparent and can be subjective, the reported effort put into the object's creation becomes a default indicator of quality. The effort heuristic is widely used among different types of individuals (including self-identified experts) and across domains, indicative of its general appeal as a basis for judgement. So, while effort can indeed be a generally reliable indicator of quality, there are instances where it may fail to accurately reflect the true value of a work, leading to incorrect judgements of quality.

Other studies show that humans tend to prefer artworks labelled as human-created over those labelled as AI-created (Bellaïche et al., 2023). This observed preference is consistent across several judgement criteria, such as Liking, Beauty, Profundity, and Worth. Labels such as 'Human-created' or 'AI-created' can heavily influence individuals' enjoyment, trust, and valuation of the artworks, regardless of the actual creator. Interestingly, higher perceived effort leads to a greater appreciation when labelled as human-created. Similar findings were observed in the music domain. There seems to exist an 'AI composer bias' where listeners' enjoyment and quality ratings of music are influenced by their knowledge or beliefs about the composer's identity (Shank et al., 2023). People like music less and judge it as lower in quality if they believe it was composed by an AI compared to believing it was composed by a human. Even with no actual difference in the music itself, the perceived identity of the composer can significantly affect listeners' aesthetic judgements.

Intentionality (i.e. the intention of the author of an artwork) seems to be a fundamental ingredient in the evaluation of the quality of an artistic production. As art is not only a physical stimulus, but also a means of human expression and communication, the importance attached to the author's true intentionality can outweigh aesthetic assessment. Creation indeed involves conceiving a mental concept for the artefact (by an author) and then physically manufacturing it (by an instrument), typically within a single individual. The concept of Mental Primacy (Judge et al., 2020) emphasises that the generation of ideas (mental labour) is valued more than the execution of those ideas through physical labour, in Western societies. Intellectual Property laws reflect this by protecting an author's mental concepts, sometimes even before their physical realisation. Is it grounded in the belief that mental and physical processes complement each other in the creation process, producing a more valuable artefact. This notion implies that a material artefact's true value is released when an idea is embodied through skilful and effortful physical work. Both the mental and physical essences of makers are transmitted to the material artefact. This influences how artefacts are valued and perceived in terms of authenticity, ownership, and connection to the creator. Folk theories of artefact creation significantly impact human-artefact relations, affecting how people evaluate different types of artefacts and their makers. Such theories can shape cultural materials and influence societal views on production and consumption. Other cultures have different preconceptions about value and authenticity (see for instance Coleman (2001), who shows that paintings considered inauthentic from a Western perspective may be authentic within Aboriginal contexts).

The perceived value of an artwork is heavily influenced by whether an object is categorised as art, which can be shaped by the creator's intent, and not just by its functional use (Newman & Bloom, 2012). People's judgements about the value of art are influenced by the intentions of the original maker to make the object a work of art or artefact. This ties in with the notion that artistic achievement is inherently linked to the artist's intention and the unique process of creation. In the economic sphere, consumers have a special appreciation for handmade products, viewing them as more attractive compared to machine-made products. This perceived value is known as the 'handmade effect'. One reason for the handmade effect may be that consumers believe handmade products are imbued with love (Fuchs et al., 2015). This belief would come from the perception that artisans invest personal care and affection into the production process. Despite rapid technological advancement in manufacturing, human craftsmanship is unlikely to become obsolete. Handmade products fulfil a consumer desire for goods that embody human attributes like love and care, which cannot be replicated by machines. Skills associated with hand making products are thus likely to remain valuable in the labour market due to consumer preferences for goods made with human touch. This is an interesting parallel to be drawn with the case of AI-generated content: one can hardly imagine that

human creation will lose its value anytime soon. The question is rather to understand how people attribute value to human creation.

3. Rethinking with AI our relationship with the world and with others

Beyond questions of production and effort, the growing presence of AI also invites a broader reflection on how humans relate to the world and to one another. Human interaction is structured by the ability to perceive others as intentional agents and to coordinate attention around shared goals and meanings. As shown in Michael Tomasello's work on shared intentionality (Tomasello et al., 2005), these capacities are foundational to communication, cooperation, and learning. Attention is therefore not merely a cognitive resource for selecting information, but a social process that enables individuals to align their actions and interpretations with those of others.

Preserving we-mode interactions

Another way to characterise the social nature of attention is through the concept of the "we-mode" (Gallotti & Frith, 2013). In we-mode situations – such as attending a live lecture or watching a sporting event – individuals experience a shared flow of attention with others. Empirical research suggests that shared attention increases the cognitive resources allocated to information that is jointly attended to. The hypothesis of Shteynberg et al. (2020) is that **shared attention increases the allocation of cognitive resources dedicated to information**, which is the object of attention of the social group. Sandberg suggests that when people believe they are acquiring information with members of their group (information that is a priori likely to be encountered in subsequent social interactions), it becomes more psychologically salient. From an evolutionary point of view, better processing of such information would increase the individual's readiness for group coordination and collective action.

This idea is closely related to Gergely and Csibra's Natural Pedagogy Theory (2009), according to which humans are uniquely sensitive to communicative cues signalling that information is intended to be transmitted and shared. When information is recognised as shared knowledge, individuals engage with it more deeply, taking into account the intentions and perspectives of others. By contrast, information that is not perceived as socially shared tends to be processed more superficially, without the same degree of contextual and interpersonal integration.

As part of a research project on future scenarios in June 2020, Stefania Broadbent conducted in-depth interviews with students in Milan, during the lockdown of Covid 19 (Broadbent et al., 2024). The main finding was that, when students complained of not being able to concentrate during remote lectures, the reason was not just a lack of ability to focus. It was mainly that there was no one present with whom they could share their attention. The distraction was due to environmental factors, but also to a lack of engagement. A live lecture is a shared experience, offering a common focus that enhances attention and concentration. It offers content that is shared both cognitively and socially, a common foundation on which to build various forms of coordination, collaboration and solidarity

The case of human-machine interactions

The systematic integration of AI into many applications raises major questions for joint attention. When using ChatGPT for instance, users spend a considerable amount of time generating instructions to achieve the required result, via the development of prompts. A significant part of this time is spent trying to guess how the system will respond and react. The impossibility of identifying what the system knows, and on what information its responses are based, makes it almost impossible to anticipate its

responses, which often leads to accepting what is proposed in an uncritical way, or rejecting suggestions out of hand. For several years now, AI has been criticised for its lack of transparency, but this is often about the mechanisms underlying algorithmic decisions. The problem also lies in the cognitive nature of human-machine interaction. **The impossibility of anticipating and reading an artificial mind, without a theory of mind, reduces the possibility of cooperation, and confronts the human with the alternative of accepting or rejecting the solution proposed by the system.**

In our social interactions and epistemic practices, we rely on reputation mechanisms to judge the value of information (Origgi, 2018). How we should position ourselves with regard to information coming from such an opaque system is not straightforward. In the socio-ethnological sense, culture presupposes the awareness of fine-grained nuances of language, objects and social situations, and the ability to choose the right word or action. This implies the acquisition of a coherent set of automatisms enabling us to interact with certain dimensions of the environment, in a given situation. Developing a culture of attention means increasing each person's ability to make themselves accessible to many rich microworlds (Broadbent et al., 2024).

The problem with opaque algorithms is that they impose worldviews

For many experts, the development and use of large language models in natural language processing is leading to significant risks for society, including the propagation of biases, perpetuation of harmful stereotypes, and the production of misleadingly fluent but potentially harmful content without accountability (Bender et al., 2021). While some algorithms are indeed biased, due to the data on which they have been trained, the overall prevalence of bias remains relatively limited (relative to the base frequency). Greater risks lie in the use of discriminating categories, and in unfounded reliance on AI tools, rather than in biases inherent in the algorithms themselves. The temptation to call for absolute transparency is strong, but one might in fact wonder to what extent is such transparency necessary, or even desirable. The question of how and to whom this transparency could be really useful is not trivial. There is in fact a certain incompatibility between clarity and understandability, because good explanations often require the use of intuitive but misleading representations. Rather than making absolute demands in terms of transparency, we need to consider the conditions for informed confidence on the part of users in AI-based systems. In other words, transparency should not be called for its own sake, but to allow for informed confidence.

The references mentioned in this report are available in the Bibliography of KT4D Social Risk Toolkit Module B: AI, trust and awareness. (<https://zenodo.org/records/18375398>)

KT4D

Knowledge Technologies
for Democracy

@kt4democracy.bsky.social

KT4Democracy

Funded by
the European Union